

Input Parameters Selection for Emotion Recognition using Genetic Algorithm and Machine Learning

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Abstract— In the literature, the recognition of human facial emotions has been greatly improved. However, the big challenge is to train efficient and fast algorithms due to the large volume of input data. This article presents a novel method to investigate seven human classic emotions: angry, disgusted, happy, neutral, sad, surprised, and afraid. Instead of using information vectors of all pixels extracted from the image, the present study works with 7 Euclidean distances considering keypoints of the face: corners of the mouth, eyes, and tip of the nose, in addition to the mean and variance of the face region, 9 input attributes, in total. In addition, we verified through neurogenetic algorithms whether it is possible to use one-dimensional data as information carriers for the classification of facial emotions. Two classification algorithms were performed separately: Support Vector Machine and Multi-Layer Perceptron. Then, the genetic algorithm was applied to select the most suitable input attributes for each architecture. With this we analyzed which variables were relevant for the classification. The database of facial emotions used were the The Japanese Female Facial Expression (JAFFE) and Extended Cohn-Kanade Dataset (CK+) containing 188 and 902 images, respectively. The best result was found for the MLP architecture with 3 input attributes selected. The global average accuracy found was 80.9%, being 100% and 95% for the prediction of happy and neutral emotions, respectively.

Keywords — *Computer Vision, Human Emotion, Machine Learning, Genetic Algorithms.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The introduction of facial expressions is, in reality, to appear what we feel in social environment. Facial expressions are a method of non-verbal communication. In arranging for a facial expression to be captured, the beneficiary must have the capacity to recognize the expression, decipher its meaning, get its inspiration and react to it. This prepared whole in which this non-verbal communication gains space is social cognition [1,2].

Social aspects of human communication can change over time. But regarding the biological and physiological aspects of facial expressions, behavioral facial expressions are similar between different individuals and across cultures, countries and ages. Some of these topics are important questions to be studied and applied to computational modeling [3,4].

According to Paul Ekman's thinking, there are a total of 7 fundamental facial expressions recognized by the vast majority of individuals, regardless of their nationality, level of knowledge or culture. The expressions in Ekman's catalog are happiness, sadness, anger, fear, surprise, contempt and disgust [5].

The benefits displayed from projects and improvements in algorithmic arrangements able of interpreting facial feelings from human faces are modern conceivable outcomes for human-computer intelligent, content composing, as in mechanical autonomy, recreations, computerized marketing, cleverly assistance and recovery frameworks, among numerous others [6]. The sooner the improvement and enhancement of calculations for facial elucidation happens, the more effective the role of innovation in understanding normal ranges of the human sciences, such as brain research, neuroscience, human cognition and learning [7,8].

Within the past decades, deep learning is one of the branches of artificial intelligence and is being broadly connected within the field of computer vision [9]. The zone of computer vision includes forms such as: Image Classification, Object Detection, Image Segmentation, Semantic Segmentation, Image Reconstruction, among others. In this way, a wide variety of application areas can be taken from pre-processing to the calculation and preparation of information obtained by computer vision. [10,11].

In common, before the image data goes through the processing stage, it is appropriate to extract some features [11,12]. We are able to classify these highlights in two groups: global and local image features. Figure 1 shows an illustration of dependent behavior and amount of data related to global or local image features. The main topic of interest before extracting information from the image is a cautious approach to the pre-processing step regarding relevant features or even resizing images that can lead to loss of information and volume of extracted input data [13].

In recent years, the systematic review study by Canal et al. (2022) presents the state-of-the-art concerning the interpretation and recognition of human emotions from facial expressions. This review presents the principal techniques used in this field [14]. In essence, it presents as “classical” approaches those algorithms based on a face detection procedure followed by some recognizer capable of interpreting the feature vector and making some decision according to a fixed number of output classes. These approaches usually are Support Vector Machines (SVM), Naive Bayes, among others.

On the other hand, they present techniques based on neural networks, as NNB methods. In this manner, the input layer of those NNB methods contains a discretization of the facial image or more commonly vectors of local features extracted using some feature descriptor method [14]. Related to NNB techniques, CNN is on the rise lately in many areas such as: medical image classification, object labeling and facial emotion recognition [3,4,7,15,16,17,18]. Meantime, the

CNNs are not considered in this paper due to the fact that our input information is one-dimensional.

Fig. 1. Representation of A) Global and B) Local extraction feature vectors from images.

In addition of computational field that has been widely used in artificial intelligence technologies is the Genetic Algorithm (GA) [19,20]. Genetic Algorithms are globally optimized logical algorithms that are based on genetic and natural selection mechanisms. These type algorithms are commonly utilized for partition of blind sources of biological evoked electrical potentials, estimation of torque and control of prosthesis movements. For a binary genetic approach, the population is created in binary shape. Each gene on a chromosome is represented by the specific bits: 0 and 1 [21,22].

The objective is to verify through neurogenetic algorithms if it is possible to use one-dimensional data to transport information and be used as input variables filter for classification of facial emotions in the field of computer vision. This study considered the keypoints of the face: eyes, right and left corners of the mouth and tip of the nose, mean and global variance of pixels of the facial image.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Database

Two private databases were used: Extended Cohn-Kanade Dataset (CK+) and The Japanese Female Facial Expression (JAFFE). The databases contain 902 images and 188 images, respectively. It must have a request to obtain access to both databases. The classes of emotions present in both datasets are: Neutral, Sad, Happy, Afraid, Surprised, Disgusted and Angry. The facial images were collected with static individuals performing different expressions, one for each expression performed.

B. Data Pre-Processing

The code processing was developed in Python language. The facial expression images were divided into seven classification categories, from 0 to 6. The qualitative classes were replaced by numbers. The mapping is 0-Angry, 1-Disgusted, 2-Happy, 3-Neutral, 4-Sad, 5-Surprised and 6-Afraid.

The pre-processing calculation at that point goes through the registries with the pictures and automatically writing spreadsheets with the explanatory values of the information related to the feeling category. The open-source library RetinaFace is utilized to distinguish and crop the facial region, in expansion to collecting the coordinates of keypoints such as eyes, nose and mouth corners[23].

The input parameters to bolster the preparing calculations are measurable values of the edited face picture, mean and variance and the Euclidean distances calculated from the face arranges. This processing comprises five facial keypoints: right eye (OD), left eye (LE), nose (N), right corner of the mouth (BD) and left corner of the mouth (BE).

From this, the distances visualized in Figure 2 are calculated as: Right Eye-Nose (N-OD), Right Eye-Right Mouth Corner (OD-BD), Left Eye-Nose (N-OE), Left Eye-Left Mouth Corner (OE-BE), Nose-Right Mouth Corner (N-BD), Nose-Left Mouth Corner (N-BE) and Right Mouth Corner-Left Mouth Corner (BD-BE).

Fig. 2. To the left are the geometrical facial keypoints. To the right are the five keypoints selected: Right Eye (OD), Left Eye (OE), Nose (N), Right Mouth Corner (BD) and Left Mouth Corner (BE).

C. Data Analysis

Agreeing to the consider Canal et al. (2022), a survey of the structures of feeling acknowledgment calculations was carried out, isolating between two bunches: classical and neural network-based approaches [14]. The foremost common strategies, except from CNNs, for analyzing one-dimensional information from each category are: Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP). For this reason, both models were chosen and utilize in this study.

The Genetic Algorithm was used as a selector of input traits for machine learning. Depending on the level of positive or negative relationship of the considered features, the exactness of the classifier can be improved or disabled. In this way, the population of 30 individuals with 9-bit binary chromosomes was merged to the input information. A total of 30 elite individuals were chosen and 10 tournaments, 3-3 competitions were held to select the leading individual.

The fitness function considered was the accuracy displayed by the technique applied, MLP or SVM. Advance, for a more extensive variability of individuals the crossover and mutations were performed individually with 80% and 50% probabilities of event.

For both the SVM and the MLP, the test group was considered 25% of the overall. For the SVM calculation, the sigmoid kernel was utilized. For the MLP calculation, 4 hidden layers with 30, 30, 30 and 13 neurons were utilized, individually. With the iterations value set to 3500.

III. RESULTS

The results will be divided into two datasets analyzing: JAFFE and CK+. At first, considering Table 1, there are presented the accuracy values with and without the genetic algorithm application to input parameters for different

methods: Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP).

According to the JAFFE dataset, when there is no selection of inputs, the average accuracy between the categories is 30% for SVM and 63.8% for MLP. When we manipulate the selection of parameters with GA, the accuracies increase of 12.6% and 7%, respectively.

Still considering Table 1, related to CK+ dataset, when there is no selection of inputs, the average accuracy between the categories is 74% for SVM and 71.3% for MLP. When the GA is inserted to parameters selection, the accuracies also increase of 3% and 9%, respectively for machine learning algorithms SVM and MLP.

TABLE I. METHODS FOR ANALYZING INPUT PARAMETERS AND AVERAGE ACCURACY RATE FOR EACH DATABASE JAFFE AND CK+

Method	GA	JAFFE	CK+
SVM	No	30%	74%
SVM	Yes	42.6%	77%
MLP	No	63.8%	71.6%
MLP	Yes	70.2%	80.9%

Focusing extensively on JAFFE dataset, the Figures 3 and 4 plot the confusion matrices. It is possible to observe the relation of accuracy among all the categories. Related to Figure 3, the classes 2, 3, 5 and 6 achieved above 50% with GA for SVM architecture. In this method the parameters selected was the following vector [1, 0, 0, 0, 1, 0, 0, 0, 1]. In this way, the selection of parameters consisted of pixels mean value, N-BE and BE-BD.

According to the MLP architecture, still analyzing from JAFFE database, the Figure 4 shows the confusion matrix with average accuracy over all classes, and it reached 70.2%. All categories, except from class 6, overpass 60% of accuracy. Highlighting for category 1, it reaches 100%. In this method the parameters selected was the following vector [1, 1, 0, 1, 1, 0, 1, 0, 0]. In this way, the selection consisted of pixels mean value, pixels variance value, OE-BE, N-BE and N-OE.

Fig. 3. Confusion matrix by SVM algorithm with GA reached 42.3% average accuracy. JAFFE Database.

Considering the CK+ dataset, the Figures 5 and 6 shows the confusion matrices for SVM and MLP architecture. The classification of the SVM algorithm reached 77%. The input selection was the chromosome [0, 1, 1, 1, 0, 0, 1, 1, 0], consisted of pixel variance value, OD-BD, OE-BE, N-OE and N-OD parameters selected. Among all the categories, the

classes 2, 3 and 5 reached 90%. Related to MLP algorithm, the average accuracy between all categories was almost 81%. The resulted chromosome was [0, 0, 0, 1, 0, 0, 0, 1, 1] selecting the three inputs, OE-BE, N-OD and BE-BD. Among all the categories, the classes 2, 3 and 5 reached 95%. The happy category presented 100% of true positive predictions.

Fig. 4. Confusion matrix by MLP algorithm with GA application reached 70.2% average accuracy. JAFFE Database.

Independently of the processing method some categories have the performance better than other categories. For example, the categories 2, 3 and 5. And, considering the categories 0, 1, 4 and 6, it is clear that fine adjustment reflects direct on their hit rate classification. The worst category for classification depends on the architecture and dataset, but we can highlight a difficult rate for categories 0 and 6.

Fig. 5. Confusion matrix by SVM algorithm with GA application reached 77% average accuracy. CK+ Database.

Fig. 6. Confusion matrix by MLP algorithm with GA application reached 80.9% average accuracy. CK+ Database.

The Figure 7 shows the ROC Curve for MLP Classification, using GA selection for CK+ database. A ROC

curve was designed by category, but it is also conceivable to draw a ROC curve considering each component as a parallel expectation (micro-average). Another evaluation score for multi-label classification is the macro-average, which gives equal weight to the classification of each label. Macro-media display around 68% of true positive rate, and micro-average around of 87%. To encourage information and dissemination of results, the code is accessible in a repository [24].

Fig. 7. ROC Curve by MLP with GA among all trained classes. CK+ Dataset.

IV. DISCUSSION

Previous studies were done in this thematic field by the current research team and this article presents advances in promising results considering two datasets JAFFE and CK+.

Canal et. Al (2022) states a literature review of widely used techniques for labeling human facial emotions. As showed by their study, classical techniques, SVM and others, and based on neural networks, CNN, MLP and others, are presented. Recently widely used, there are neural network based classifiers such as CNN, MLP architectures, among others. Specifically the CNNs architecture, by the method of image resizing, can lead to loss of image information [13]. In contrast, the present study aims to analyse facial keypoint coordinates and statistical variables of faces, mean and variance. This simplification of the input attributes, one-dimensional input data, is focused on reducing the volume of information analyzed while maintaining the desired efficiency among human emotions.

There are two mainly human facial expressions images mainly used in literature: CK and CK+. The CK dataset features has 486 available video sequences with 7 emotion classes as well [25]. The CK+ dataset features 593 video sequences (30 fps) available with 7 emotion classes [26].

From a classic approach, considering CK dataset, the Slimani et. Al (2018) shows that the highest average accuracy among the classified classes, present in the literature, is 92.40% [27]. According to Lopes et. Al (2017) the highest accuracy was found which average system accuracy reached 96.76% with NNB approach, in 2017, with the CK+ dataset [28].

The benefits of using facial coordinates is that the information analyzed is not interfered with by different ambient lighting and is independent of the individual's skin tone. Also,

the facial movement, which is an obstacle for other methods, as long as the facial coordinates are detected, the movement does not generate noise or major problems.

The genetic algorithms display a few benefits on their application which are: parallelism, global optimization, a bigger set of arrangement space, probabilistic based in nature determination, hereditary representations utilizing chromosomes [29]. As our study presented investigation of 9 input attributes, we would have 9!-1 conceivable combinations, barring an entirely invalid chromosome. Considering the endless sum of possibilities it would be exceptionally time expending on the off chance that tried manually.

Based on the reasons specified above, this article carried out preparing an approach with SVM, considered as a classical approach and MLP as an approach based on neural network techniques. The most important point of this article to be highlighted is the small dataset, and considering, in total, nine input data variables from pictures: average and variance pixel value, OD-BD, OE-BE, N-BD, N-BE, N-OD, N-OE and BD-BE. Just over 900 pictures, the CK+ dataset MLP method reached 80.9% average with only 3 input variables, OE-BE, N-OD and BE-BD, for 7 classes of facial expressions in total. In case of the volume dataset increments, this effectiveness and precision of classification might upgrade.

In the present study, related to JAFFE, the classes that presented the best performance, considering MLP method were disgusted, happy and neutral. The worst were surprised and afraid. For CK+, the best emotion classifications were happy, neutral and surprised. The worst presented angry, disgusted, sad and afraid emotions. In accordance with the state-of-art, it is showed that the best ratings for happy and neutral emotions just over 95% of the classifying algorithms [26]. The failed emotion classifications are afraid and sad emotions [26].

The limitations of the present study is the complete front locale face should be identified within the picture of the discover the coordinates. Plus, as another disadvantage is the fact that the facial point must be detected, in other words the environment illumination interferes directly in algorithm accuracy. At last, some sophisticated emotions such as comtempt were not considered because it would require more facial points to be considered.

In future study, we point update the number of facial keypoints considered and make strides the machine learning calculations with genetic algorithm to discover the finest architecture considering number of covered up layers and each number of neurons.

V. CONCLUSION

Expanding number of distinctive applications for the classification of facial emotions by machine interfacing, in recent years, modern methods and classification strategies have been applied This study points to confirm by neuro-genetic algorithms if it is possible to utilize one-dimensional information to carrier data for feeling classification. From the Euclidean separations between keypoints of the face: corners of the mouth, eyes and tip of the nose, we concluded that the MLP engineering displayed an normal precision of 80.9% considering the entire of 7 classes, being 100% of accuracy for happy emotion.

From the application of AG in both SVM and MLP input variables, the best predicted classes were with MLP archi-

ecture. The highlighted emotions were angry, disgusted and happy for JAFFE. And happy, neutral and surprised for CK+. Following state-of-art statements. From 9 input attributes, the AG selected 5 for JAFFE in MLP method: mean value, pixels variance value, OE-BE, N-BE and N-OE. And selected 3 input variables for CK+ : OE-BE, N-OD and BE-BD.

While both datasets used has just over 180 and 900 images, respectively, it is believed that the greater the number of images the better chances of modeling accuracies of each label. In addition, this article is in accordance with the state-of-art, showing that approach with facial keypoint coordinates may be encouraging in facial emotion recognition field.

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